

Weekly Progress Report

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Introduction:

- In this report, we summarize the trouble shooting did in this period to fix the following problem:

Continual voltage dips in V_MCU which have been recurrent since July and no longer responding to a reset of the node.

- We speak about a collaboration with RC1 to extract data from the sensors.dat file
- We also speak about our work in the Bergen Prototype Evaluation

Plans:

- To remove one of the report masks and investigate the response
- To complete and send version 1 of the Bergen Prototype Evaluation Document

Activities:

- According to Robert, there could be an issue with one of the sensors. He suggested a removal of the AD chip (MCP3424) report mask as a technique to unit test (incremental troubleshooting) to identify the faulty modules. This was done and the voltage dips seem to have stopped.
- In extracting the data from sensors.dat, several parallel mechanisms were employed using seltag (Mary) and custom applications in python (Emmanuel) and C# (Max). The last two focusing on an improved user interaction with the application.
- The evaluation document of the Bergen prototype was completed and sent. Responses started coming in almost immediately.
- Redesigning the WIMEA-ICT website on the pi. Link <http://129.177.63.214/newsite>
- Review and selection of collaboration tools. We selected github <https://github.com/wimea-ict> as a code repository, <https://zenodo.org/collection/user-wimea-ict> for documents and <http://teamup.com> for schedules and calendars. Each of the RC3 students created a work plan on provided the link to the supervisors and advisors.